

1 **Next-generation sequencing of human epidermal keratinocytes with human papillomavirus E7**
2 **expression.**

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7 We measured total transcription in human epidermal keratinocytes by RNA-sequencing following
8 expression of HPV16 E7 for discovery of novel E7-associated functions in human cells. We report here
9 activation of *Idh1* by E7 of HPV16. Cells expressing E7 additionally and specifically activated enzymes
10 *Mettl21a* and *Mettl7a*.

11 Citations

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